

1 **Habitat complexity reduces feeding strength of** 2 **freshwater predators**

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30

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34 the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

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35 **Statement on inclusion**

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36 This experiment was conducted in the UK, by a German and Spanish research team.

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37 **Data availability statement** – Our data, code and statistical methods are available on GitHub
38 (<https://github.com/b-c-r/CRITTERdata>, <https://github.com/b-c-r/CRITTERcode>, and <https://github.com/b-c-r/CRITTERstatistics>) and as citable versions on Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15348769>,
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39 **Abstract**

40 1. The physical structure of an environment potentially influences feeding interactions among
41 organisms, for instance, by providing refuge for prey. We examined how habitat complexity
42 affects the functional feeding response of an ambush predator (damselfly larvae *Ischnura*
43 *elegans*) and a pursuit predator (backswimmer *Notonecta glauca*) feeding on the isopod
44 *Asellus aquaticus*.

45 2. We ran experiments in aquatic microcosms with an increasing number of structural
46 elements (0, 2, or 3 rings of plastic plants in different spatial configurations), resulting in five
47 habitat complexity levels. Across these levels, predators were presented with different prey
48 densities to determine the functional response pattern. The experimental design and analysis
49 allowed us to test for effects of structure presence, amount, and complexity level on
50 functional response in one pass, without confounding predictors.

51 3. The feeding for both predators across all complexity levels was best described by a type II
52 functional response model, and habitat drove feeding strength. Regarding the latter, the
53 predators showed different responses to the complexity treatments. The overall feeding rate of
54 *I. elegans* was mainly explained by the absence vs. presence of structure. Yet, in the case of
55 *N. glauca*, feeding rate was strongly dependent on habitat complexity with the predator
56 showing a unique maximum feeding rate (i.e. the inverse of the handling time) for each
57 complexity level and a decreasing attack rate with increasing amount of habitat.

58 4. On average, prey consumption by both predators was reduced when complex structures
59 were present, compared to the 'no habitat structure' environment (e.g. consumption more than
60 halved for some treatments). Our findings demonstrate that habitat complexity dampens
61 feeding rates and therefore plays a key role in the stability of freshwater ecosystems.

62

63 **1. Introduction**

64 The physical structure of an environment is a crucial factor in shaping community
65 composition and the ecological processes driven by living organisms. Habitat complexity has
66 been shown to influence population density, body size, and species richness of invertebrates
67 in both terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems (Flores et al., 2016; Soukup et al., 2022; White &
68 Walsh, 2020). Furthermore, habitat complexity is also likely to influence the interactions
69 among organisms by providing more refuge, thereby reducing predation risk for prey,
70 especially when prey densities are low (Barrios & O’Neill et al., 2015; Hauzy et al., 2010;
71 Orrock et al., 2013; Vucic-Pestic et al., 2010a,b). Indeed, previous studies have demonstrated
72 that increasing habitat complexity can lower predation pressure on prey, thus reducing the
73 top-down control exerted by predators (Chang & Todd, 2023; Kalinkat et al., 2013; Mocq et
74 al., 2021). Yet habitat complexity could also aid predators in their search for prey, particularly
75 those operating in three-dimensional environments (Pawar et al., 2012), as observed in the
76 case of a freshwater copepod preying on ciliates (Reiss & Schmid-Araya, 2011). Therefore,
77 habitat complexity can potentially modify or shape energy flows through food webs,
78 influencing feeding relationships between resources and consumers and among predators and
79 prey.

80 Functional response models are a suitable tool when it comes to addressing the effects
81 of habitat complexity on species interactions, as they describe the relationship between prey
82 density and the intake of prey by a predator (Holling, 1959a; Li et al., 2018). More generally,
83 functional response models have been central in understanding interaction strengths,
84 population dynamics and ecosystem stability (Berlow et al., 2009; Kratina et al., 2022; Rall et
85 al., 2008; Williams & Martinez, 2004). Characterizing an organism’s feeding behaviour (in

86 short-term experiments), feeding rate, F , is a function of prey density, N , and determined by
87 the time required for predators to find, attack, capture, handle, and ingest their prey (Holling,
88 1959a; Li et al., 2018). When observing feeding rate for a range of increasing prey density,
89 then these rates often have a hyperbolic saturating shape, called the type II functional
90 response (Figure 1a). The initial increase in the feeding rate, F , is driven by the attack rate,
91 a , which was originally termed ‘instantaneous rate of discovery’ (Holling, 1959a); and other
92 synonyms include the terms capture-, filtration- or search rate. The handling time, T_h , controls
93 the saturation of the curve (Figure 1a). Alternatively, the function can be written using the
94 maximum feeding rate, $F_{max} = 1/T_h$, and the half saturation density, $N_{half} = 1/(aT_h)$ - i.e.
95 the prey density where half of the maximum feeding rate is reached (Real, 1977; Figure 1a).
96 Following the ‘Holling approach’ (i.e. models that use attack rate and handling time *sensu*
97 Holling, 1959a) and the ‘Real approach’ (i.e. models using maximum feeding rate and half
98 saturation density *sensu* Real 1977), the full functional response models are

99
$$F = \frac{aN}{1+aT_hN} = \frac{F_{max}N}{N_{half}+N} \quad (1).$$

100 In addition to the hyperbolic shape, other functional response patterns are observed,
101 for instance Holling (1959b) reported an s-shaped functional response for mammal predators
102 under field conditions. The s-shape (type III response) can be observed when both the
103 feeding- and attack rate are a function of prey density, meaning that the predator optimizes
104 hunting prey with increasing prey density. The simplest way to include this feature in the
105 above models is to assume a linear increase in the attack rate, $a = bN$, with b being the
106 attack coefficient (Juliano, 2001). Dubbed the generalized functional response model, this
107 approach allows for a seamless switch from a type II functional response to an s-shaped type
108 III functional response (Figure 1b), promoted by many modelling studies (Jeschke et al.,

109 2004; Kalinkat & Rall, 2015; Rall et al., 2008; Williams & Martinez, 2004). Here, attack rate
110 is a power-law function of prey density ($a = bN^q$). If the ‘shape parameter’ q is 0, the
111 functional response is type II, and if the shape parameter q is 1, the functional response is a
112 ‘strict’ type III response (Kalinkat et al., 2023). The generalized functional response models
113 are

$$114 \quad F = \frac{bN^{1+q}}{1+bT_h N^{1+q}} = \frac{F_{max} N^{1+q}}{N_{half}^{1+q} + N^{1+q}} \quad (2).$$

115 Despite being a commonly reported functional response type (Jeschke et al., 2004;
116 Kalinkat & Rall, 2015) the type II functional response is known to produce unstable
117 population dynamics, especially under environmental enrichment (e.g. Rall et al., 2008;
118 Rosenzweig, 1971). In contrast, the s-shaped functional response is known to stabilize
119 population dynamics and enhance biodiversity, at least in modelling studies (Rall et al., 2008;
120 Williams & Martinez, 2004). The difference of the hyperbolic type II and s-shaped type III
121 functional response can be explained by the differences in predation risk (Figure 1b). The
122 stabilizing effect of the type III functional response can be due to a low predation risk per
123 prey individual (Figure 1b inlay). Generally, prey growth increases more slowly than
124 predation risk, resulting in a low but stable population that remains constrained by top-down
125 pressure (in contrast to a type II response).

126

127

128 **Figure 1.** (a) The type II functional response (bold line) is either controlled by the parameters
 129 attack rate, a , and handling time, T_h (Holling 1959b), or the maximum feeding rate F_{\max} and
 130 the half saturation density N_{half} (Real 1977). (b) The generalized functional response model
 131 allows for a seamless shift between the hyperbolic type II functional response ($q = 0$) and a
 132 ‘strict’ type III functional response ($q = 1$). Inlay: The predation risk of a single prey item
 133 decreases in the case of a hyperbolic type II functional response ($q = 0$); when the function
 134 becomes s-shaped (type III) the predation risk increases with increasing prey density, leading
 135 to small but stable populations. (c) Example where the Holling and Real models (shown in
 136 [a]) are interchangeable. The feeding rate decreases primarily at low prey densities. Although
 137 it appears that the maximum feeding rate also declines, this is misleading; in reality, the
 138 maximum rate is simply reached at much higher prey densities. (d) Example where the
 139 models are not interchangeable. The variation in feeding rates as a function of parameter
 140 values is clearly visible. The feeding rate decreases uniformly across all prey densities, i.e. the
 141 decline is proportional and independent of prey density.

142

143

144 The detection of an s-shaped (type III) functional response remains methodologically
145 challenging (Kalinkat et al., 2023) and some researchers argue that apparent type III responses
146 might mainly arise from statistical artefacts rather than from underlying biological
147 mechanisms (DeLong et al., 2025). Undeniably, the experimental design is critical in
148 identifying functional response patterns accurately (DeLong et al., 2025; Sarnelle & Wilson,
149 2008), and habitat presence might be a particularly influential predictor in functional response
150 experiments (Kalinkat & Rall, 2015). For instance, habitat complexity has frequently been
151 cited as a key driver of type III functional responses (Barrios & O’Neill et al., 2015; Kalinkat et
152 al., 2013; Vucic & Pestic et al., 2010a,b).

153 Testing how refuge availability and habitat complexity alter trophic relationships
154 requires careful experimental design to avoid confounding structural quantity with habitat
155 complexity (Flores et al., 2016; St. Pierre & Kovalenko, 2014). In a laboratory experiment
156 with a centipede predator and springtail prey, Kalinkat et al. (2013) observed that increasing
157 the amount of structure (adding leaves) provided more surface area for both predator and
158 prey, but did not create refuge. In the latter study, the observed changes in space-dependent
159 functional response parameters did not vary per unit surface, suggesting a dilution effect
160 rather than refuge use (Kalinkat et al., 2013). Importantly, habitat complexity can increase not
161 only by adding more structures, but also through changes in the spatial arrangement of a fixed
162 number of elements (Flores et al., 2016). Furthermore, certain forms of habitat complexity can
163 represent obstacles without contributing to available surface area (Hauzy et al., 2010).

164 In addition to habitat complexity, the predation strategy of the predator is an important
165 factor determining the interaction strength of predator and prey (Almany, 2004; Schmitz,
166 2017) and, by extension, the stability of food webs. These strategies include ‘ambush’ (also
167 known as ‘sit-and-wait’ tactics) and ‘pursuit’ (active chasing), and these traits can determine

168 spatial utilization and interactions with environmental structures (Pawar et al., 2012; Schmitz,
169 2017). For instance, ambush predators, exemplified in aquatic systems by species like
170 dragonfly and damselfly nymphs, occur in complex habitats that provide ample hiding spots,
171 enhancing their ability to remain concealed and ambush prey (Chang & Todd, 2023; Mocq et
172 al., 2021; Soukup et al., 2022). Conversely, pursuit predators, such as predatory fish, certain
173 types of predatory shrimp or backswimmers require more open and less obstructed spaces to
174 effectively chase down their prey. Dense structures within complex habitat, however, can
175 impede their navigation and reduce hunting efficiency (Almany, 2004; Warfe & Barmuta,
176 2006). Therefore, habitat complexity is likely to have varying impacts on predatory success
177 depending on the predator's hunting strategy. For instance, in aquatic environments, a more
178 complex habitat may favour ambush predators by providing increased hiding opportunities,
179 while posing challenges for active swimming predators, thereby potentially reducing their
180 hunting efficiency (Almany, 2004; Dunn & Hovel, 2020; Froneman & Cuthbert, 2022).
181 Studying how functional response of different predators is modulated by habitat structure is
182 crucial to understand trophic interactions and energy transfer through real food webs in
183 nature.

184 We aimed to explore how two different predators with contrasting hunting strategies
185 are affected by habitat complexity in their search and consumption of prey. Specifically, we
186 tested how habitat complexity (measured as [1] the presence of structure, [2] the amount of
187 structure and [3] the spatial arrangement of structure) influenced functional response
188 parameters, addressing three hypotheses as follows.

- 189 1. Habitat complexity alters the shape of the functional response curve, as more
190 structure can create refuge for prey and makes detection of prey more challenging,
191 particularly at low prey densities (Figure 1b).

- 192 2. Feeding rates generally decrease with increasing amount of habitat structure
193 (Figure 1c), resulting in altered functional response parameters. We expected that
194 attack rate rather than handling time would be affected by habitat complexity
195 meaning feeding rate would be reduced at low prey densities (Figure 1b).
- 196 3. The pursuit predator (*N. glauca*) will show a different response to habitat structure
197 compared to the ambush predator (*I. elegans*).

198

199 **2. Material and Methods**

200 **2.1 Experimental set-up**

201 The experiment was carried out using individual microcosms (9.5 cm diameter and 11.5 cm
202 high circular beakers). The prey (water hog-louse *Asellus aquaticus*) was provided with leaves
203 to feed on. Hence, air-dried alder leaves (*Alnus glutinosa* L.) were weighed, added to each
204 microcosm (2 g each) and conditioned in 500 mL water (1 part of filtered pond water to 5
205 parts of tap water) for 7 days. The water was renewed when the prey was introduced to the
206 microcosms. It should be noted that the individuals were not able to hide in the leaves, and we
207 therefore ignored the leaves in any estimates of habitat complexity. Every microcosm was
208 served by one air-stone, and it was sealed with cling film to prevent evaporation. The
209 experiment was run in a controlled-temperature room (15 °C) with a 14 h light:10 h dark
210 cycle.

211 When manipulating habitat complexity, it is important to disentangle the effects of
212 complexity *per se* from the effects of the amount of structure in the microcosm (see Kalinkat
213 et al. 2013 for detailed reasoning). We used plastic rings to create both structure and different

214 levels of complexity (Figure 2). These rings were artificial plastic plants mimicking the
215 aquatic plant *Ceratophyllum* spp. (Code No. FRF 491, Fish are Fun®). Habitat complexity
216 was created in three ways: 1. as the presence vs. absence of habitat structure; 2. as the amount
217 of structure (0, 2 or 3 of plastic plant rings); and 3. as two spatial configurations of structures
218 in the case of 2 and 3 rings (Figure 2; and Flores et al. 2016), resulting in 5 complexity levels.
219 The order of these five levels (from 'simple' to 'complex' [levels 0, 1, 2, 3 and 4]) was
220 determined by measuring the fractal dimension in the feeding arena (Figure 2; and Flores et
221 al. 2016).

222

223 **Figure 2.** Photographs of the structures used to create habitat complexity in microcosms with
224 'structure present'. The basic unit of each structure was a plastic plant strip (mimicking
225 *Ceratophyllum* spp.), joined up as a ring (~ 8 cm in diameter) and four levels of fractal
226 dimension were created with them: 1) level 1 consisted of two rings aligned, with a fractal
227 dimension (D) of 1.77; 2) level 2 consisted of two rings twisted into each other ($D = 1.80$); 3)
228 level 3 consisted of three rings locked together ($D = 1.81$) and 4) level four was a ball made
229 from 3 rings together ($D = 1.83$). Fractal dimension was used to assign a categorical value for
230 'complexity' to each treatment (zero to four). This design therefore also gave two levels of
231 'amount of structure' - 3g for complexity level 1 and 2 and 4.5 g for complexity level 3 and 4.
232 Figure taken from Flores et al. (2016).

233 **2.2 Feeding functional response**

234 We tested the feeding functional response of the ambush predator *Ischnura elegans* (van der
235 Linden) (16.8 mm average length and 3.5 mm average head width) and a pursuit predator
236 *Notonecta glauca* (L.) (14.7 mm average length and 4.9 mm average width) preying on *A.*
237 *aquaticus* (6.6 mm average body length). Applying body dimension to dry weight regressions
238 from the literature (Baines et al., 2015; Benke et al., 1999; Reiss et al., 2011), we estimated
239 these species to have an average dry weight of 8.6, 10.5 and 2.1 mg per individual
240 respectively.

241 The predators were able to get into the structures added to the microcosms, which,
242 thus, did not function as a full refuge for prey. The predators were allowed to feed for 24
243 hours. We used time blocks to run a replicate each, which were all started two days apart from
244 each other because of the time needed to sort *A. aquaticus* individuals. Further, the blocks had
245 the advantage that this approach allowed us to add ‘very high’ density treatments after
246 running the first replicate and to further adjust the number of replicates needed after observing
247 feeding during the first time block. Prey densities for *I. elegans* were 1, 3, 5, 10, 30, 80 and
248 120 individuals per microcosm. Prey densities for *N. glauca*, were 1, 3, 5, 10, 30, 80, 120 and
249 180 individuals per microcosm. Replication varied from 1 to 6 replicates per treatment
250 (mostly 3 for *I. elegans* and 6 for *N. glauca*) and in total we ran 297 microcosms. The data is
251 available on GitHub (<https://github.com/b-c-r/CRITTERdata>) and on Zenodo (Flores et al.,
252 2025).

253 **2.3 Data Analysis**

254 Equations 1 and 2 above assume that prey is replenished, however in our laboratory
255 experiments, prey density declined through time. The problem of prey depletion — and its
256 possible solutions — are described by Rosenbaum & Rall (2018). Following the latter
257 authors, we used the Rogers Random Predator Equation (Rogers, 1972; Royama, 1971)
258 modified with the Lambert W function (Bolker, 2008) to fit type II functional responses,
259 simulating prey decline (Rosenbaum & Rall, 2018). For estimating the generalized functional
260 response parameters, we directly fitted simulated time series to our data. These methods
261 prevent biased parameter estimations (see details in Rall et al., 2025a; Rosenbaum & Rall,
262 2018).

263 We first investigated if the shape of the functional response was hyperbolic or s-
264 shaped for all ten treatments (5 complexity treatments and 2 predator species). This was
265 achieved by fitting the generalized functional response model (Equation 2, Figure 1b)
266 allowing for a seamless shift between type II and type III functional responses (Rosenbaum &
267 Rall, 2018).

268 After determining the shape of the functional response, we tested a suite of functional
269 response models to address the effects of habitat on the functional response parameters (see
270 (Rall et al., 2025a). This suite of models tested for 1) the assumption that habitat does not
271 influence feeding, 2) an effect of no structure vs. structure, 3) for an effect caused by the
272 amount of structure and 4) for effects due to the complexity (fractal dimension) of the
273 structure (while being related to ‘amount’). The models targeted two parameters or three
274 parameters (case generalized functional response) at once (Table 1).

275 Testing four assumptions on two parameters in a fully factorial fashion gives a suite of
276 16 models for the ‘Holling’ approach (1H to 16H) and the ‘Real’ approach (1R to 16R) of

277 functional responses each (Table 1). We dubbed the approach using a and T_h ‘Holling’ and
278 the approach using F_{max} and N_{half} ‘Real’ as these authors were the first to introduce these
279 parameters (Holling, 1959a,b; Real, 1977). Consequently, models 1H to 16H targeted
280 parameters T_h and a (*sensu* Holling 1959a,b) and 1R to 16R targeted F_{max} and N_{half} (*sensu*
281 Real 1977). In case we detected any type III functional response, the full-factorial scheme
282 would have need 64 models for each functional response formulation (see Rall et al. 2025a).

283 In brief, the reasoning for fitting both Holling- and Real- approaches to functional
284 response models lies in testing effects of a predictor like habitat complexity. Although
285 Holling- and Real- equations can be generally translated into each other (Figure 1a, Equations
286 1 and 2), this does not necessarily work when the parameters are connected to an overarching
287 model, like in our case, habitat complexity levels. For instance, as long as both parameters
288 depend on the same habitat complexity measure (e.g. five levels of habitat complexity), the
289 parameter values of the Holling-approach and the Real-approach can be calculated from each
290 other. Yet, in some cases, models are not exchangeable, e.g. if the attack rate / half saturation
291 densities depend on the amount of structural elements and handling time / maximum feeding
292 rate are fitted to the level of complexity. This phenomenon is caused by the fact that the half
293 saturation density is not simply the inverse of attack rate but also depends on the handling
294 time. A change in maximum feeding rate, for instance, automatically leads to a proportional
295 change in attack rate, if the half saturation density is constant (see Figure 1c,d and Rall et al.
296 2025a for more details).

297 This approach allowed testing for these different habitat predictors on all functional
298 response parameters in one pass and avoided confounding ‘amount of structure’ with
299 ‘complexity’, based on the rationale developed in Flores et. al. (2016). We compared the
300 models by using both the Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC) and the Bayesian information

301 criterion (BIC), where the lowest AIC and BIC indicates the best (most parsimonious) model.
302 The output includes a point estimate for the parameter and lower and upper confidence
303 intervals (CIs).

304 Hence, the functional response models provide information about the overall amount
305 of prey eaten, driven by the maximum feeding rate or its inverse, the handling time. This
306 effect is most obvious at high prey densities, where the curve reaches its asymptote (Figure
307 1a, c). The attack rate, and the half saturation density predominantly control the feeding rate
308 at lower densities (Figure 1a, d), and we were able to compare those parameters between
309 habitat treatments.

310 We provide the underlying code on GitHub (<https://github.com/b-c-r/CRITTERcode>)
311 and as a citable version on Zenodo (Rall, et al., 2025b). This includes a README for the
312 description of the code. The latter also contain detailed theoretical and statistical
313 considerations, and methods in the supplement.

314

315 **Table 1:** Overview of models tested on two parameters at once to show if feeding rate was
 316 affected by habitat complexity. In total, four parameters are tested, yet only two of them in
 317 one pass as this reduced the testing from a possible 128 combinations to 32 models. Also, the
 318 four parameters correspond to two different simulation models (dubbed ‘H models’ and ‘R
 319 models’; after Holling 1959a,b and Real 1977, respectively). For each parameter, there are
 320 four hypotheses: ‘Zero’ assumes that habitat has no effect; ‘One’ assumes that presence has
 321 an effect (2 levels: present and absent); ‘Two’ assumes that amount has an effect (3 levels: 0,
 322 2 and 3 plastic plant rings) and ‘Three’ assumes that complexity level (fractal dimension) has
 323 an effect (5 levels: 0 to 4 complexity levels).

Parameter	‘Holling approach’								‘Real approach’								
	T_h	a				F_{max}				N_{half}							
Hypothesis	zero	one	two	three													
	habitat has no effect	presence has effect	amount has effect	complexity level has effect	habitat has no effect	presence has effect	amount has effect	complexity level has effect	habitat has no effect	presence has effect	amount has effect	complexity level has effect	habitat has no effect	presence has effect	amount has effect	complexity level has effect	
Model	Model								Model								
1H	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1R	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
2H	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	2R	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
3H	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	3R	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
4H	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	4R	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
5H	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	5R	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	0
6H	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	6R	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0
7H	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	7R	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0
8H	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	8R	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1
9H	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	9R	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0
10H	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	10R	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0
11H	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	11R	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0
12H	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	12R	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	1
13H	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	13R	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0
14H	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	14R	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0
15H	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	15R	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0
16H	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	16R	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1

1= model tests for this, 0= model does not test for this

324

325

326

327 **3. Results**

328 The shape of the functional response curves for both *N. glauca* and *I. elegans* (Figures 3 and
329 4) consistently fit best to a type II model for all five complexity levels, as established by
330 fitting the generalized functional response model to the data (Table 2). Applying this model to
331 both species and all complexity levels, the shape parameter q was never significantly different
332 from zero, hence feeding rates followed a functional response type II (Table 2).

333 Therefore, we tested a total of 32 type II functional response models (Table 1) to test
334 for the effect of habitat. For the functional response exhibited by *I. elegans*, the best fitting
335 model (both lowest AIC and BIC, Table 3) was ‘model 5R’ (Table 3, Figure 3). This model
336 assumed that the effect of structure presences vs. absence overrides all other predictors. In the
337 ‘5R’ model, F_{max} takes a value of 28 prey eaten in 24 h when no structure is present (CI: 19.4
338 to 40.8). However, when structure was present, then F_{max} was 14.6 (CI: 10.7 to 29). N_{half} was
339 not affected by the habitat and takes the value of 57 prey items per arena (CI: 34 to 94).

340 The best fitting (most parsimonious) model (both lowest AIC and BIC) for *N. glauca*
341 was ‘model 15H’ (Table 3, Figure 4) and this model assumed that each complexity level has a
342 unique handling time, T_h , and that attack rate, a , decreases with increasing amount of habitat
343 structure. Hence, the parameters that influence feeding rate are more complex in this case.
344 Maximum feeding rate (estimated from the handling time [$F_{max} = 1/T_h$]) was 31 (CI: 26 to
345 35) prey eaten in 24 h for complexity level 0 (no structure), 18 (CI: 15 to 21) for level 1, 28
346 (CI: 24 to 33) for level 2, 21 (CI: 17 to 27) for level 3 and 19 (CI: 15 to 23) for level 4 (Figure
347 4).

348 The attack rate of *N. glauca* (Figure 4) decreased with increasing number of habitat
349 structural elements (rings, $\log_{10}(a) = a_{intercept} + a_{slope}N_{rings}$), indicated by a negative
350 slope (-0.144, CI: -0.191 to -0.097).

351 The reason this more complex model was significant for *N. glauca* over the very
352 similar, but simpler, ‘presence of structure’ model, was that ‘unexpected’ responses were
353 observed when two plastic plant rings had been added to the microcosms, both in terms of
354 feeding- and attack rate (Figure 5). A possible explanation is that the configuration of two
355 rings into two different shapes creates very different habitat types and that this is not the case
356 when three rings were used (the latter essentially created an ideal hiding spot in any case, a
357 ‘dense ball’). For two rings, it is likely that one of the configurations (complexity level 2, two
358 twisted rings, see Figure 2, panel 2) left more space for the agile pursuit predator *N. glauca* to
359 navigate in (Figures 2 and 5).

360 Overall, fitting these models showed that prey consumption was considerably less for
361 both predators when complex structures were present, compared to the no habitat structure
362 environment (Figures 3 and 4). For instance, the maximum number of prey consumed was
363 less than half in some of the ‘no structure’ vs. the ‘structure’ treatments (Figures 3 and 4). To
364 illustrate this difference, in ‘no structure microcosms’, and at a prey density of 120
365 individuals, the maximum number of prey consumed was 20 and 49 for *I. elegans* and *N.*
366 *glauca* respectively. In contrast, at the same prey density, *I. elegans* and *N. glauca*
367 respectively fed on a maximum of 9 and 20 *A. aquaticus* in at least one of the structure
368 treatments (the latter were different treatments for the two species, see Figures 3 and 4).

369

370 **Table 2:** Testing for the functional response type for two predators feeding at 5 complexity
 371 levels (0 to 4), by using the generalized functional response model (Rosenbaum & Rall, 2018;
 372 Vucic-Pestic et al., 2010b; Williams & Martinez, 2004). We observed a declining proportion
 373 of prey eaten with increasing complexity level; consistent with a type II functional response
 374 (indicated by the value for the shape parameter q). The shape parameter q is not significantly
 375 different from zero in all cases; hence the feeding rate follows a functional response type II.

Predator	Complexity	q	Significance	Type
<i>Ischnura elegans</i>	0	0.116	n.s.	II
<i>Ischnura elegans</i>	1	0.047	n.s.	II
<i>Ischnura elegans</i>	2	-0.001	n.s.	II
<i>Ischnura elegans</i>	3	-0.001	n.s.	II
<i>Ischnura elegans</i>	4	0.193	n.s.	II
<i>Notonecta glauca</i>	0	-0.011	n.s.	II
<i>Notonecta glauca</i>	1	-0.006	n.s.	II
<i>Notonecta glauca</i>	2	0.194	n.s.	II
<i>Notonecta glauca</i>	3	-0.002	n.s.	II
<i>Notonecta glauca</i>	4	-0.001	n.s.	II

376

377 **Table 3:** The six best models (see Table 1 for explanation of each model) that describe the
 378 functional response parameters T_h and a (model names includes an ‘H’), or F_{max} and N_{half}
 379 (model names includes an ‘R’) and for predators *I. elegance* and *N. glauca* feeding on *A.*
 380 *aquaticus*. The full suite of models can be found in Rall et al. (2025a). The best fit of the
 381 models was tested using AIC (AIC generally performs better for models that have more
 382 parameters) and BIC. A low value indicates the best fit.

AIC			BIC		
Model	df	dAIC	Model	df	dBIC
<i>Ischnura elegance</i>					
Model 5R	3	0.000	Model 5R	3	0.000
Model 7R	4	0.265	Model 5H	3	1.583
Model 6H	4	0.952	Model 7R	4	2.731
Model 6R	4	0.952	Model 6H	4	3.418
Model 5H	3	1.583	Model 6R	4	3.418
Model 13R	6	2.107	Model 7H	4	4.718
<i>Notonecta glauca</i>					
Model 15H	7	0.000	Model 15H	7	0.000
Model 16H	10	1.274	Model 9R	3	1.004
Model 16R	10	1.274	Model 11H	4	1.485
Model 15R	7	1.990	Model 11R	4	1.485
Model 14R	7	4.189	Model 13R	6	1.507
Model 13R	6	4.854	Model 15R	7	1.990
Model 12H	7	8.352	Model 7H	4	2.516

383

384 **Figure 3.** Functional response curves for the ambush predator *I. elegans* feeding in
385 microcosms (arena) without structure **(a)** and in arenas with plastic plant structure **(b)**. The
386 right panel (b) shows data across four habitat complexity levels because the most significant
387 statistical model for the *I. elegans* feeding pattern was the difference between complexity
388 level zero (no structure) and treatments with structure present. Grey shaded areas denote the
389 95% confidence intervals.

390

391

392

393 **Figure 4.** Functional response curves for the pursuit predator *N. glauca* in feeding arenas with
394 different complexity level created with plastic plant rings (see images in panels b to e and
395 Figure 2). Habitat complexity levels 1 and 2 (b, d) were created with two rings of plastic
396 plants, while levels 3 and 4 (c, e) had three rings of plastic plants. All five habitat complexity
397 levels are shown (and not summarised in one panel as in Figure 3) because the most
398 significant statistical model for the *N. glauca* feeding pattern assumed that each complexity
399 level has a unique handling time, and that attack rate decreases with increasing amount of
400 habitat structure. Grey shaded areas denote the 95% confidence intervals.

401

402 **Figure 5.** The functional feeding response parameters (a) F_{max} and (b) T_h of *N. glauca* feeding
403 on *A. aquaticus*. The amount of structure (number of plastic plant rings) is regressed against
404 maximum feeding rate (a) and handling time (b). When two rings were added, there was an
405 ‘unexpected response’ (high parameter values for complexity level 2) - explaining why a
406 more complex model that assumed an effect of complexity level (levels zero to 4) is more
407 parsimonious compared to assuming that ‘amount of structure’ solely drives the response.
408 Grey shaded areas denote the 95% confidence intervals.

409 **4. Discussion**

410 Our findings suggest that habitat complexity affects predator-prey interactions in freshwater
411 ecosystems. Results from our feeding experiments showed that feeding, i.e. the functional
412 response type, did not significantly vary with habitat complexity (all feeding was consistent
413 with a type II response). However, we found support for the hypothesis that increased habitat
414 complexity would decrease feeding rates overall. Both the ambush predator (damselfly larvae
415 *Ischnura elegans*) and the pursuit predator (backswimmer *Notonecta glauca*) showed higher
416 feeding rates in microcosms without structures compared to those with structure. Weighing
417 8.6 and 10.5 mg (dry weight, dw, per individual) respectively, *I. elegans* and *N. glauca* fed on
418 *A. aquaticus* individuals weighing 2.1 mg dw each. For example, at a prey density of 120
419 prey, average consumption reached over four (*I. elegans*) and eight (*N. glauca*) times of
420 predator body weight in 24 hours (20 and 33 prey eaten on average by *I. elegans* and *N.*
421 *glauca* respectively). The latter assumes that prey was ingested whole (which was not the case
422 for *N. glauca*, which left prey body parts after feeding). Taken together, this suggests that
423 complexity affected energy flow considerably and that, while habitat complexity reduced
424 feeding rates by affecting F_{max} , attack rate and handling time, the overall mechanisms (shape
425 of the functional response curve) remained consistent across different complexity levels.

426 Generally, it is known that complex structures offer refuge for prey, thereby reducing
427 the efficiency of predators (Froneman & Cuthbert, 2022; Hauzy et al., 2010; Mocq et al.,
428 2021). This reduction in feeding rates due to increased habitat complexity implies a decrease
429 in the top-down control of predators on prey populations (Chang & Todd, 2023). In our study,
430 the reduction in feeding rates was associated with both a reduction in attack rate and an
431 increase in handling time (i.e. an increase in maximum feeding rate while the half saturation

432 density is relatively constant). However, the magnitude of these changes varied across
433 different complexity levels. Previous studies, conducted using microcosm approaches, have
434 shown that attack rate and handling time can respond differently to habitat complexity. For
435 instance, a study on the zooplankton prey *Arcartia longipatella* and the predator
436 *Mesopodopsis wooldridgei* reports strong complexity effects on attack rates (Froneman &
437 Cuthbert, 2022). Yet, the dragonfly larvae *Aeshna cyanea* preying on *Chaoborus obscuripes*
438 larvae was shown to change handling time with complexity (Mocq et al., 2021). Soil mites
439 preying on collembolans displayed varying response in both attack rate and handling time
440 with habitat structure (Hauzy et al., 2010).

441 Overall, these previous studies also demonstrate that whether habitat is perceived as
442 ‘complex’ by the organisms is context-dependent and that the size proportions of predator to
443 prey – and to habitat – are a key factor. For instance, in feeding experiments with the
444 predatory nematode *Prionchulus muscorum* addition of structure had little effect as predator
445 and prey had the same body shape and mobility - hence the feeding pattern was mainly driven
446 by prey size (Kreuzinger-Janik et al., 2019). Estimating fractal dimension to assign an
447 ‘objective’ complexity level (i.e. a score from low to high) proved valuable for our
448 experiment (see also Flores et al. 2016) but it was obvious that one of the predators (*N.*
449 *glauca*) was more successful than expected in one case because the structure had much open
450 space, despite its high fractal dimension. Therefore, finding a metric for habitat complexity
451 should include spatial arrangement and consider the dimensions of prey, predator and habitat
452 structure. Clearly, it is important to add this form of realism in laboratory experiments as
453 abiotic factors, such as habitat structure (e.g. Flores et al. 2016) or temperature (e.g. Sentis et
454 al., 2022), can change the outcomes of feeding experiments. More complex physical structure
455 could have a positive effect on overall performance of an assemblage (Flores et al., 2016)

456 because species can feed in their optimum environment (in analogy to their optimum
457 temperature) while predation is dampened. The amount or arrangement of physical structure
458 could, therefore, influence consumer effects and could be an important predictor to consider
459 in ecological research that focuses on energy transfer and ecosystem functioning (Flores et al.,
460 2016).

461 We hypothesized that at lowest habitat complexity (i.e. microcosms without added
462 plastic plant structures), the shape of the functional response would best fit to a type II
463 functional response because feeding rates would be mainly limited by the time required by the
464 predator to kill and eat its prey. With increasing habitat complexity levels, we expected a
465 sigmoid functional response (i.e. type III functional response), as at low prey densities the
466 efficiency of the predator would be limited by the structures offering multiple hiding places
467 (Kalinkat et al., 2013; Vucic-Pestic et al., 2010a,b). (However, as prey density increases and
468 the amount of refuge becomes saturated, the efficiency of the predator would again increase at
469 intermediate prey densities (Figure 1b,c).

470 Yet, functional response of both predators was consistently best described by a type II
471 model across all the levels of habitat complexity. Mikolajewski et al. (2015) highlighted a
472 phenotypic plasticity for *Ishnura*, allowing it to adapt to environmental changes while
473 maintaining a type II functional response. Moreover, our design of the habitat structure
474 allowed both predators to enter the potential prey refuge, which may also be a reason for not
475 finding a type III response. One prey per predator was the lowest density in our experiment,
476 which corresponds to a density of 140 individuals per square metre, but in nature, lower
477 abundances, can be observed for many taxa (Larrañaga et al., 2009). Indeed, not considering
478 low prey in laboratory set-ups can hinder the detection of a type III response (Sarnelle &
479 Wilson, 2008). Although the prevalence of type III functional response has been postulated as

480 the way to maintain stability of prey populations and high diversity (Kalinkat et al., 2023;
481 Murdoch & Oaten, 1975; Rall et al., 2008), type II is still the most common functional
482 response in feeding studies (DeLong et al., 2025; Dunn & Hovel, 2020; Kalinkat & Rall,
483 2015). Even though a type III functional response was not supported by our data, we saw a
484 hint that the interaction of both predators and its prey was stabilizing as feeding rates
485 generally decreased with the presence and with increasing complexity of the habitat structure.
486 The general decrease in interaction strength is associated with more stable population
487 dynamics and higher species richness in model food webs (May, 1972; Rall et al., 2008;
488 Yodzis & Innes, 1992).

489 The two predators in our experiment differed in terms of their predatory strategies, and
490 the functional response parameters highlighted some of those differences. The pursuit
491 predator (the backswimmer *N. glauca*) exhibited three times the attack rate of the ambush
492 predator (the damselfly *I. elegans*), although a similar handling time, when no structures were
493 present in their environment. Furthermore, as an open-water hunter, *N. glauca* is more likely
494 to operate in a 3D environment (Pawar et al., 2012) compared to *I. elegans* that sits within or
495 on the habitat surface. Indeed, dimensionality of consumer search space is probably a major
496 driver of species coexistence, and the stability and abundance of populations (Pawar et al.
497 2012).

498 As predicted, the effect of habitat complexity was stronger for the pursuit predator
499 than the ambush predator. An explanation is the barrier effect that the structures can create for
500 the pursuit predator, reducing the visibility of prey and the capture success (Grabowski &
501 Kimbro, 2005). In agreement with Svensson et al. (2000), habitat heterogeneity significantly
502 reduced predation efficiency in *N. glauca*, highlighting the vulnerability of pursuit predators
503 to habitat complexity. Previous studies have also shown that *Notonecta* spp. are more

504 successful in open environments (Gittelman, 1974), and that factors such as water depth and
505 refuge availability influence its hunting behaviour (Cockrell, 1984).

506 Our short-term experiment with three species certainly demonstrated that habitat
507 complexity is a key factor to be considered when it comes to trophic interactions. Both
508 predators were more successful in environments without structure and were able to feed on
509 substantially more prey in this open environment. We conclude that habitat complexity has
510 the potential to shape species interactions and carbon flow within the food web. The results of
511 this study demonstrate that increased habitat complexity significantly reduces feeding rates in
512 both *I. elegans* and *N. glauca*. The reduction in predation efficiency, driven by decreases in
513 attack rates and increases in handling times, supports the idea that structural complexity
514 provides refuge for prey, limiting predator success. Despite these changes in feeding rates,
515 both species maintained a type II functional response across all levels of habitat complexity,
516 indicating that while habitat structure affects predator efficiency, it does not fundamentally
517 alter the shape of the functional response curve. Overall, these findings underscore the critical
518 role of habitat complexity in shaping trophic interactions and sustaining energy flow. In more
519 complex, natural ecosystems, habitat complexity will drive species coexistence, stability of
520 food webs and diversity of communities.

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